

THE IMPORTANCE OF MISTREATMENT TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING

Karimova Dilorom Shavkat qizi,
scientific employee of the
Andijan Machine-building Institute
e-mail: karimovadilorom15@gmail.com
phone: +998900600661

Abstract: *This paper is concentrated on the outline of technology role in English teaching and learning. globalization has created a replacement world order for doing business. New data and communication technologies (ICTs) have dramatically modified the means we have a tendency to live, learn, work, and even suppose work. The natural process of mixing globalization with new technology has had dramatic economic and social impacts embody in English teaching and learning. The role of technology media is required in learning process wherever media isn't as a tool however as a part of integral in academic system and learning process.*

Keywords: *Technology, English Teaching and Learning. A. Introduction throughout last many decades, one in all the foremost exciting changes in education is expounded to the word ‘‘technology’’.*

Though some debates relating to the effectiveness of technology have existed most researchers agree that technology is used effectively as a psychological feature tool furthermore as an instructional media. For example, Bruce counsel that technology is useful in room settings by encouraging inquiry, serving to communication, constructing teaching products, and helping students' self-expression. Globalization has created a replacement world order for doing business. New data and communication technologies (ICTs) have dramatically modified the means we have a tendency to live, learn, work, and even suppose work. The natural process of mixing globalization with new technology has had dramatic economic and social impacts. It's created new opportunities furthermore as new challenges and

uncertainty. Several staff is dislocated, whereas a big variety of children are structurally out of work or underemployed. Skills polarization between so- referred to as mind or data staff and unskilled-low-knowledge has widened the gap in financial gain inequalities. The expansion of English Teaching through Technology With the fast development of science and technology, the rising and developing of multimedia system technology and its application to teaching, that includes audio, visual, animation results comes into full play in teaching and sets a good platform for reform and exploration on English teaching model within the new era. It's evidenced that multimedia technology plays a positive role in promoting activities and initiatives of student and teaching effect in English class. Technological innovations have gone hand – in hand with the expansion of English and are ever-changing the means within which we have a tendency to communicate. It's honest to claim that the growth of the net has expedited the growth of English people language which this has occurred at a time once computers aren't any longer the exclusive domains of the dedicated few, however rather accessible to many. With this there has been a awfully vital proliferation of literature relating to the utilization of technology in teaching. Principally these writings without ambiguity settle for technology because the most essential half in teaching. in an exceedingly sense, a bent to stress on inevitable role of technology in pedagogy to the extent of obscurant human teacher by technology part has been terribly dominant. And as a result if we have a tendency to neglect or ignore technological developments they're going to continue and maybe we are going to ne'er be able to catch up, no matter our discipline or branch. For this reason it's necessary for language academics to remember of the newest and best instrumentation and to possess a full data of what's accessible in any given situation. Academics will use multimedia system Technology to present additional colorful, stimulating lectures. There are several techniques applicable in varied degrees to learning situation. Some are helpful for testing and distance education, and a few for teaching any subjects. The teaching

principle ought to be to understand new technologies within the areas and functions wherever they supply one thing resolutely new useful and ne'er let machines take over the role of the teacher or limit functions where additional ancient ways in which are superior. There are various reasons why all learners and academics should acumen to create use of the new technology. Here we have a tendency to additionally have to be compelled to emphasize that the new technologies develop and spread so quickly that we cannot avoid their attraction and influence in any type several of the studies have stressed technology as a medium for enhancing room teaching. This study can incorporate similar concepts. In general, the term technology shall represent comparatively new electronic media adore computers, video, and also the associated hardware, networks, and computer code that change them to function. this can be what the majority have in mind after they discuss the utilization of technology in faculties. Most academics settle for technology within the classroom as a mixture of each ancient media such as OHP, slide, and videotape and new media as well as information and communication technology. that specialize in the educational and teaching process, states the roles of technology in 5 ways: - having the ability to bring the real-world experiences into the classroom. - providing system that enables learners to participate in complicated psychological feature tasks. - increasing opportunities to receive refined and individualized feedback. - building communities of interaction between teachers, students, parents, and alternative interested. - increasing opportunities for teacher development. In addition, states some impacts of technology on students achievement: (1) mastering elementary skills (2) turning into practiced users of technology (3) getting ready students with 21st century skills (3) motivating students to higher level of achievement. From on top of statement, we are able to see however necessary the roles and contribution of technology in term of teaching and learning process. This truth supported the author in conducting this analysis. coaching Clearly, research has shown that pc training absolutely impacts academics' attitudes toward technology. Explored secondary teachers' and

students' attitudes toward creative person Internet-based learning environments. They administered a form to lxxviii teachers across Taiwan. Interestingly, the teachers rated simple use as their most significant think about integration the creative person Internet-based learning settings. This simple use issue was rated on top of alternative factors of the technology-based learning environment adore reflective thinking, vital judgment and epistemic awareness. This study highlights the very fact that academics, whereas doubtless positive about mistreatment technology, are still uncomfortable with introducing it into their rooms. Vryzas found that the bulk of teachers believe that using computers within the classroom improves their status; however fewer want to create technology coaching for teachers compulsory. Whereas the authors saw this as a contradiction and took the read that the teachers were not willing to attempt to mistreatment technology within the room, it's maybe additional of an indictment of the kind of coaching offered to academics. In another example, found that teachers are more seemingly to specialize in external obstacles to integration, adore hardware accessibility and inadequate materials instead of that specialize in internal obstacles, such as adequate technical knowledge. Again, the man of science is vital of the teacher rather than the type of training that's offered to the teacher. Brown studied 3 post-secondary teachers who used technology in their classroom to differing degrees. This article was designed to illuminate a number of the problems academics face once mistreatment technology for learning. On the topic of coaching, one academic that was profiled command a certificate in tutorial technology, however failed to read herself as an knowledgeable. Additionally, her fellow teachers did not understand her as an expert either even supposing they were attentive to the certification. this time highlights the trend within the literature that whereas teachers want technology training, teachers might perceive the training they receive as lean for quality technology integration into the classroom. Self-addressed teacher beliefs and technology training, stating that the technical skills approach is insufficient to deal with academics' needs. Instead, he advocates anchoring

technology coaching within the context of teachers' beliefs concerning teaching, learning and also the roles of each teachers and learners in this process. In Arrington's view, teachers ought to begin by evaluating their own views of 'worthwhile, attainable and relevant' teaching and learning. Further, teachers should detail their notions of adequate technical support for his or her endeavors. Solely once the teacher is well familiar on his/her own views of teaching and learning should technical choices enter the discussion. In fact, the teacher's individual views on teaching and learning can likely dictate the kind of technical training that's applicable for his/her own wants and desires, creating the training relevant and timely. Interestingly, Arrington's read of coaching wouldn't solely address the academics' perceived frustrations with technology training, it might additionally permit teachers to figure through their paradigm shift problems self-addressed within the previous section. This twin purpose makes the additional time this approach might take worthy and after all maybe necessary. Involving the reason above, the angle of teacher ought to be positive. The teacher should amend their paradigm shift and follows some training.

Conclusion: technology is extremely important for academics in teaching English. The utilization of technology as media in room is extremely helpful. Furthermore, media technology will increase the students' attention-grabbing in learning process. The angle of teacher ought to be positive. The teacher should amend their paradigm shift and follows some training.

REFERENCES

1. Adler-Kassner, Linda, Crooks, Robert,&Watters, Ann. 1997. "Service learning and composition at the crossroads."
2. Press. Bruce, B., & Levin, J. 2001. "Roles for new technologies in language arts: inquiry, communication, construction, and expression."
3. "Educational Technology Research and Development" 42(2), 7–19. Mehlinger, H. D., & Powers, S. M. 2002.

4. Technology & teacher education: “A guide for educators and policymakers.”
Mikolchak, Maria. 2006.
5. “Creating Studrnts Centre Classrooms.” In www.apple.com/education/research. Solanki D.S, M.phil, 2012.